

DAMAGE INDUCED ANISOTROPY IN ISOTROPIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of both an experimental analysis and a modelization of the influence of damage on a virgin isotropic material. The experimental study consisting of tensile and biaxial tests clearly demonstrate the existence of a damage yield point. Micrographic analyses show the different crack orientations and forms depending on the type of loading. The proposed behaviour model is based on the formulation of a damage criterion. It allows the stress-strain relation to be correctly simulated and accounts for the anisotropy induced in the course of the tensile tests.

1 - INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behaviour of isotropic composite materials obtained from glass fibres pre-impregnated with thermosetting matrix (SMC), is similar to the behaviour of materials with oriented long fibres, at least in terms of the encountered physical phenomena. because of, given their common matrix, the viscoelastic behaviour can be determined using the same type of equation.

According to Howard and Hollaway (1987), the creep can be correctly represented using the model developed by Schapery (1969). The non-linear viscoelastic behaviour is thus well modelised.

As far as damage is concerned, the SMC materials develop the same kinds of micro structural defects as the long fibre reinforced materials, namely the occurrence of micro-cracks in the matrix. The main difference between these materials lies in the orientation of these defects. In the case of long fibre reinforced materials, the defects are parallel to the fibres while in the case of the SMC materials, the defect orientations depend on the stress directions (Mallik 1988).

This important difference leads to significantly different modelizations of their mechanical behaviours.

In the large majority of cases, the models applied to the long fibre reinforced materials are not treated by Continuum Damage Mechanics (C.D.M.). Several

methods are used, (Hashin 1983), self-consistent models for instance, which allow the determination of the damaged stiffness if the crack density and the stiffness of the virgin materials are known (Laws and al. 1983) .

In the case of statistically isotropic SMC materials, the behaviour is easier to interpret based on C.D.M. but it is necessary in this case to define a variable which can correctly represent the damage.

2 - SOME EXPERIMENTAL ASPECTS OF THE BEHAVIOUR OF PRE-IMPREGNATED POLYESTER GLASS MATERIALS

The experimental study was performed on sheets of polyester with calcium carbonate reinforced by glass fibres. The statistically isotropic behaviour is easily demonstrated by tensile tests on specimens removed from the sheet along different orientations. The tests performed are either simple or combined uniaxial tests, or biaxial tests performed using a bulging machine designed at the Laboratoire de Mécanique Appliquée (C. Siqueira, 1993).

2.1 Uniaxial Tests

- Simple tensile tests

The stress-strain curve clearly shows a significant non-linearity starting from a critical stress of 30 MPa. Progressive repeated loading tests (PRL) allow the nature of this yield point to be better understood. For tensile stresses smaller to 30 MPa, the material is elastic. If the stress is exceed the yield point, the loading-unloading curve presents a hysteresis (Figure 1). The following loading curve is identical to the preceding quasi-linear unloading curve until the maximum stress of the last cycle is reached. After this point, the non-linear behaviour is observed again.

Figure 1 : P R L test

- Combined Tests

This test consists of a series of two simple tensile tests, each one having different stress directions. To perform these tests, an entire sheet is used as a first specimen and is loaded by a stress that allows the damage yield point to be exceeded.

A verification is made to make sure that the particular shape of the specimen does not perturb the stress-strain curve. A specimen having an orientation θ with respect to the loading axis is removed from the damaged sheet. A standard tensile test is then performed on this specimen.

- $\theta = 90^\circ$

The resulting behaviour is hardly distinguishable from the virgin material. The yield point remains at 30 MPa and the elastic modulus is unchanged. The initial damage is passive.

- $\theta = 45^\circ$

While the general form remains the same (Fig. 2), the numerical values vary significantly : The yield point increases, the initial elastic modulus decreases, the slope following the non-linearity is larger than in the case of the simple test.

Figure 2 : combined test $\theta = 45^\circ$

2.2 Biaxial Tests

Two types of loadings have been applied one with normal identical stresses ($\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$) and the second such as $\sigma_1 > \sigma_2$. These two tests show also that the non-linearity yield point is reached when the values of the maximum stress is close to 30 MPa.

2.3 Micrographic analysis

In tensile tests or combined tests the micro-cracks are flat and oriented perpendicularly to the tensile axis. For the combined tests, there are two families of defects which disoriented by θ degree (photo 1).

Photo 1 : Detail of a crack orientation in combined test $\theta = 45^\circ$

3 - MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR

3.1 Choice of a damage variable

The concepts of strain equivalence the effective stress lead to, as Chaboche (1979) has proposed, the definition of the damage variable $\underline{\underline{D}}$ as a fourth order tensor.

$$(1) \quad \underline{\underline{D}} = \underline{\underline{I}} - \underline{\underline{\tilde{S}}}^{-1} : \underline{\underline{S}}$$

where $\underline{\underline{\tilde{S}}}$ et $\underline{\underline{S}}$ represent the compliance of the damaged and virgin material respectively. Without loosing any generality, this variable can be reduced by studying the loading in plane stress, which allows the simplification and the reduction of $\underline{\underline{D}}$ to a second order tensor $\underline{\underline{D}}$ (notation without any underlining). Perreux and Oytana (1993) have demonstrated that in the case of a constant orientation crack distribution perpendicular to the axis 1, $\underline{\underline{D}}$ can be written :

$$(2) \quad \underline{\underline{D}} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ D_{21} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

The coefficients D_{ij} are related in the following way by a polynomial equations that can be written for the case of an isotropic material.

$$(3) \quad C_{11}D_{21} = C_{12}D_{11}$$

$$(4) \quad \frac{D_{11}(1 - D_{66})C_{66}}{D_{66}(1 - D_{11})C_{11}} = \frac{(1 - D_{11})C_{11}S_{11} + D_{11}}{(1 - D_{11})C_{11}S_{11}}$$

where the coefficients S_{ij} , C_{ij} are respectively the elements of a compliance and stiffness tensor. it is easily shown that for the material used in this study :

$$(5) \quad D_{11} > D_{66} > D_{21}$$

The formulas for transforming to rectangular coordinates is obtained as well (C. Siqueira 1993) :

$$(6) \quad \bar{\mathbf{D}} = \mathbf{T}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{T}$$

It is also shown that the tensor resulting from two distinct damages represented by \mathbf{D}^1 , \mathbf{D}^2 is obtained from the following equation:

$$(7) \quad \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{D}^1 + \mathbf{D}^2 - \mathbf{D}^1 \cdot \mathbf{D}^2$$

3.2 The damage criterion of the behaviour's law

The experimental results show that the damage criterion can be written (figure 3):

$$(8) \quad \text{Sup}[\sigma]_{ij} = \sigma_c = 30 \text{ MPa}$$

Figure 3 : Damage criterion

In fact, the uniaxial tests show that the criterion equation can be transformed in order to integrate the influence of damage.

The following generalisation of criterion is proposed :

$$(9) \quad \text{Sup}[(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D}) \cdot \sigma]_{ij} = \sigma_c$$

Figure 4 shows that the results correspond closely with experiments in the uniaxial case. Concerning the tensile tests, the consistency equation expresses the kinetics of D_{11} :

$$(10) \quad \begin{cases} \sigma_1 \dot{D}_{11} = \dot{\sigma}_1 (1 - D_{11}) & \text{Si } \text{Sup}[(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D}) \cdot \sigma]_{ij} = \sigma_c \\ \dot{D}_{11} = 0 & \text{Si } \text{Sup}[(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D}) \cdot \sigma]_{ij} < \sigma_c \end{cases}$$

Figure 4 : Damage versus Stress (the data are obtained from PRL tests)

Equations (3,4) result in the complete determination knowing of \mathbf{D} . As for the behaviour, the experiments show that the permanent strain is, in the monotonic tests (without compression) directly related to the damage's value (Frund 1990). A simple law can be proposed allowing its determination in a P.R.L test :

$$(11) \quad \begin{cases} \varepsilon_{11}^D = \alpha D_{11} + \beta D_{11}^3 & ; \quad \alpha, \beta \text{ are constants} \\ \varepsilon_{ij}^D = 0 & \quad i = 1 \quad \& \quad j = 1 \end{cases}$$

Finally the tensile behaviour model allows the total strain ε to be determined by :

$$(12) \quad \begin{cases} \dot{\varepsilon} = \dot{\varepsilon}^c + \dot{\varepsilon}^d \\ \dot{\varepsilon}^c = \mathbf{S} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D})^{-1} \cdot \dot{\sigma} + \mathbf{S} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D})^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{D}} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D})^{-1} \cdot \sigma \end{cases}$$

The identification of the parameters α, β is performed on P.R.L. tests. The model can then be used to provide an accurate simulation of these test results (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 : Simulation of PRL tests

3.3 Validation of the model

The combined tests can then be easily simulated. The use of the equations 10, 3, 4 and 6 allow the calculation of the damage values obtained after the first test in the axis of the second, disorientated by θ . Equation 7 allows the calculation of the damage resulting from two distinct defect families. The simulations performed for $\theta=90^\circ$ show the lack of influence of the initial damage.

For $\theta=45^\circ$ the simulation (Fig. 10) is very accurate, and the experimental phenomenon being qualitatively represented.

Figure 6 : Simulation of combined test $\theta=45^\circ$

4 - CONCLUSION

The model proposed here is based on a damage criterion which gives the kinetics of the chosen damage variable. It allows simulations of the behaviour to be performed for uniaxial tests. The anisotropy induced the behaviour by the damage is apparent in the results of the combined tests and this phenomenon is well simulated by the model. A special test was designed to perform biaxial tests which proves to be very useful in determining the damage criterion.

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